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WAYS TO IMPROVE MARKETING SERVICES IN A FURNITURE MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISE

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Abstract: This article examines the complexity of the furniture production process and the high impact of technology, the fact that the production of modern furniture requires sophisticated technologies, the production of new types and models of furniture, the long-term service of consumers from the product, and the fact that consumers spend a relatively large amount of time on the selection and purchase process of goods.

Key words: Furniture products, consumer, assortment, service, process, price, technology.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mebel ishlab chiqarish jarayonining murakkabligi va texnologiyaning yuqori ta'siri, zamonaviy mebel ishlab chiqarish murakkab texnologiyalarni talab qilishi, mebelning yangi turlari va modellarini ishlab chiqarish, mahsulotdan iste'molchilarga uzoq muddatli xizmat ko'rsatish va iste'molchilarning tovarlarni tanlash va sotib olish jarayoniga nisbatan ko'p vaqt sarflashlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Mebel mahsulotlari, iste'molchi, assortiment, xizmat ko'rsatish, jarayon, narx, texnologiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются сложность процесса производства мебели и высокая степень влияния технологий, а также то, что производство современной мебели требует применения сложных технологий, разработки новых видов и моделей мебели, длительного срока службы продукции потребителями и того, что потребители тратят относительно много времени на выбор и покупку товара.

Ключевые слова: Мебельная продукция, потребитель, assortiment, услуга, процесс, цена, технология.

INTRODUCTION

Market research is a comprehensive analysis of the current state of the market, including an assessment of demand, supply, price trends and the competitive environment. In Uzbekistan, against the backdrop of active economic reforms and updating the legislative framework, market research is of particular importance for effective strategic planning and management decision-making.

In recent years, the country has been implementing the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", aimed at comprehensive modernization of the economy and society. Within the framework of this strategy, special attention is paid to creating favorable conditions for entrepreneurial activity, developing market relations and ensuring fair competition. These areas are reflected in the updated version of the Law "On Competition" (ZRU-850) dated July 3, 2023.

The new Law "On Competition" introduces the concept of antitrust compliance, revises the conditions for determining a dominant position in the market and establishes new criteria for economic concentration transactions. These changes are aimed at preventing market monopolization, supporting small and medium-

sized businesses, and protecting consumer rights. The introduction of these standards requires market participants to carefully analyze and adapt their strategies in accordance with the new rules.

In addition, in October 2023, the Presidential Decree “On additional measures for accelerated industrial development” (UP-169) was adopted. The document provides for the development of proposals and comprehensive measures based on a study of market conditions to meet the needs of the domestic market and prevent sharp price fluctuations. This emphasizes the importance of systematic monitoring and analysis of market conditions to ensure stability and sustainable development of the economy. Thus, in the context of updating the legislative framework and implementing strategic initiatives, studying the market situation in Uzbekistan is becoming an integral element of effective management and planning. A comprehensive analysis of market conditions allows for timely identification of trends, adaptation to changes and making informed decisions that contribute to the sustainable development of business and the economy as a whole.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy. Many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their practical application, including F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. .We can include famous scientists like Marshall.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing, while the research carried out in the field of marketing in our country for many years was based on national characteristics. R. Ibragimov to them. Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, D. Rakhimova, SH. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musayeva and others can be included.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The marketing activities of “GULOBOD” LLC are similar to those of all furniture enterprises in the region. In this case, market research, organization of product policy, pricing and sales promotion schemes depend on the initiative and capabilities of the enterprise. We can see this from the data in the table below (table).

Table 1. Analysis of the sales network at “GULABAD” LLC in 2024

t/r	Name of the points of sale	Sales volume, pcs.	Sales volume, million soums
1	Navobod Dier Store	2339	3101.0
2	Dealer in store	324	679.3
3	Bukhara dealer store	46	103.0
4	Shop Tashkent Dier	128	377.1
5	Store Fergana dealer	11	94.8
6	OOO «Havas Comfort Furniture»	108	76.1
7	Sam-Karpo Design Dealer	2328	3260.3
8	F-2 orders	5836	1688.7
9	F-3 orders	129	29.9
10	Individuals	201	640.8
11	Legal entities	2740	1644.7
	Total	14190	11695.8

Table 2. Structure of sales volume at “GULABAD” LLC in 2024

t/r	Name of the points of sale	Sales volume, pcs.	Sales volume, million soums
1	Selling furniture products through dealers	5284	7691.6
2	Spare parts for furniture	5965	1718.7
3	Individuals	201	640.8
4	Legal entities	2740	1644.7
	Total	14190	11695.8

According to the results of the study, it was necessary to study some of our national characteristics in the implementation of furniture product marketing. That is, it turned out that the possibility and effectiveness of marketing application significantly depends on the type of market, the products being produced and sold, and the scale of competition in the market. In particular, the lack of universal, standard, unified recommendations in the application of the marketing concept is significant, and in practical marketing everything depends on external and internal factors, consumer characteristics.

If 5-6 years ago in Uzbekistan the «total» approach prevailed in the application of the marketing concept, now the differentiated approach is widely used. If we analyze the furniture products produced by type of content, 58 percent is household furniture, 39 percent is institutional furniture, and three percent is other furniture. A significant share in this regard is office furniture and special furniture for educational institutions, retail stores, hospitals, restaurants, shops, warehouses, hairdressing salons, etc.

Analysis of the structure of furniture production by region showed that the main part of the furniture produced in 2024 was sold to the city of Samarkand and the region. The share of sales by region was as follows: to the city of Tashkent -377.1 million soums, to Fergana region -94.8 million soums, to the city of Karshi679.3 million soums, to the city of Bukhara - 103.0 million soums..

As noted above, the sustainable development of any industry is directly related to the production and sale of goods that are in demand. This, in turn, requires the effective organization of marketing activities of industry enterprises, regular research of the furniture market, taking into account consumer preferences, and a detailed analysis of the factors of the purchasing process. Technological change, the increasing role of social media, demographic changes, and the increase in women's purchasing power are the main aspects that should be taken into account in the marketing work of furniture manufacturers and retailers. We found it appropriate to segment our country's furniture consumers based on history, culture, customs, traditions, and the nature of furniture products.

«GULABOD» If we observe the activities of the LLC, from the time of its establishment to the present day, a wide range of goods occupies the main part of the assortment. From this it can be concluded that these two furniture manufacturing enterprises are applying certain differentiation strategies in terms of specialization.

Table 3. Features of the product range of “GULABAD MEBEL” LLC

“HAVAS COMFORT FURNITURE” LLC	«GULABAD FURNITURE» LLC
Targeted at middle and low-income buyers	Targeted at middle and high income buyers
The assortment mainly includes kitchens and upholstered furniture.	A wide range of products has been formed
The furniture is made using standard technology and has a low level of differentiation.	The furniture is made in a modern individual style, guaranteed to meet all types of samples in the catalog.
Orders for any furniture repair are accepted.	Does not repair furniture (except during the warranty period)
There is a possibility and orders for the production of components	No spare parts are produced.
Individual items of furniture sets are also produced.	Only orders are created for collections
The trademark has not been formed.	Produces products under the MONDELUX trademark

From the above analysis, it is clear that “HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL” LLC and “GULABAD MEBEL” LLC specialize in separate segments of the furniture market and together try to cover the market.

When purchasing furniture, consumers use a wide range of information, i.e.: they analyze various information, try to find the optimal purchase option, choose a product based on their lifestyle, taste and capabilities. The consumer also takes into account financial, technical, time loss and psychological risks when purchasing a long-term product.

The buyer performs the actions of purchasing and using home appliances only after clarifying his need, which consists of several interconnected stages. That is, the overall need is focused on solving the following problems:

- determines what type of furniture will fully meet his needs;
- The product is sold from the market, the company isbuys from the mine or via the internet;
- What are the advantages of the product, what warranty does the seller provide, and how long can this product be used?

To what extent do media influence the purchase of furniture? The analysis shows that when purchasing home appliances, 52.5% of the population uses television programs, 43.1% uses newspaper and magazine advertisements, 49.7% visits company stores, and 50.6% uses catalogs and brochures.

Furniture manufacturers need to improve the positioning process in order to achieve competitive advantage and ensure a stable position for their products in the target market and in the minds of consumers, clearly different from competitors' products. Enterprises in this industry are directing significant efforts in implementing marketing activities to the formation of a marketing complex. As a result, the positioning process, which plays an important role in the systematic and effective conduct of marketing activities by enterprises, is lagging behind. When positioning a product, special attention should be paid to developing customer awareness and modernizing it.

Improper organization of the positioning process in furniture manufacturing companies can lead to the following negative consequences:

- If the manufacturer does not determine the position of the product in the market, in this case the consumer can perform this task himself, and the company may not be able to achieve the position it expects, and may even lead to the formation of a negative image;

- Failure to clearly indicate the product's unique features that distinguish it from competitors' products, or positioning it close to competitors' positions, may serve to discourage consumers from purchasing the product, rather than to motivate them to do so;

- The lack of a clear positioning of the product can hinder the formation and consistency of the marketing mix, and may even lead to conflicting strategies for forming each element of the marketing mix.

- Even if the position is clearly chosen, but if its boundaries are narrowly defined, such positioning can act as a force that hinders the expansion of the market for the company's existing products and the introduction of new products. The main reason for this is that companies in the industry use a common brand strategy.

Based on the above, furniture manufacturers should focus on two main areas when implementing the positioning process:

- Determining the point of relevance or, in other words, the point of similarity of the positioned product. That is, based on research, it is intended to determine in the minds of consumers which product category the enterprise's product is equated with, or rather, which category it is included in. This, in turn, makes it possible to identify its direct competitors based on revealing the specific characteristics of the product category.

- Identifying the point of differentiation of the positioned product. This involves demonstrating the competitive advantage of the product by identifying one or more unique features that clearly distinguish it from competitors' products.

- Furniture manufacturers should consider the following specific features of the industry before positioning themselves in the above-mentioned areas:

- The complexity of the product production process and the high impact of technology. The production of modern furniture requires sophisticated technologies, which ultimately leads to an increase in the market price of the product.

- The length of the period for launching the production of a new type and model of furniture. The average period for launching the production of a new model of furniture for large furniture manufacturers is 7-15 months.

- High demand for product quality. Since furniture is a type of product that requires prior selection, consumers expect the product to provide long-term service. In order to maintain the quality of their products at a high level, manufacturers use high-quality fittings in their production, while maintaining their functional properties. Therefore, many companies use the words "quality" and "durable" when positioning their products.

Warranty service. Usually, the costs of warranty and post-warranty service are not high, but in some cases they can amount to 20-25% of the product cost. Also, after-sales furniture assembly service can be up to 10% of the product cost.

The consumer spends a relatively large amount of time on the product selection and purchase process. Marketing research shows that in the consumer goods market, a consumer can spend up to 4 weeks on selecting and purchasing furniture.

The above problems and the specifics of marketing activities in furniture production highlight the need for enterprises to develop a strategic and tactical program for a separate marketing service.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Being aware of market trends and consumer demands in Uzbekistan is essential to expanding the company's position and position in the furniture market. By adopting sustainable practices, offering traditional designs, having a strong online presence, and using natural and organic materials, Gulobod LLC can address current market trends in Uzbekistan and expand its position in the market. Analyzing statistical data and understanding market trends, conducting research and analysis, innovating products, and collaborating with local designers and craftsmen also provide the company with ample opportunities to gain a competitive advantage, succeed in this dynamic industry, and achieve long-term success in the market.

We offer the following methods for studying different consumer behavior patterns and their application to Gulobod LLC in the furniture industry:

1. Surveys. Surveys are one of the most common and effective ways to study consumer behavior, and developing effective survey methods is essential to collecting reliable data. Surveys can be conducted both online and in person, and they are used to collect quantitative data on topics such as shopping habits, product preferences, and brand loyalty.

2. Focus groups. Focus groups are another effective way to study specific consumer behaviors in Uzbekistan. Focus groups typically consist of a small group of consumers who are asked to discuss their opinions and attitudes toward a particular product or service. Focus groups can provide qualitative data on topics such as product design, packaging, and pricing.

3. Online analysis. In today's digital age, online analytics has become an increasingly important tool for studying specific consumer behaviors. Online analytics is the process of obtaining valuable insights into consumer behavior by monitoring consumers' interactions with a company's website, social media accounts, and other online platforms. Online analytics also involves collecting and analyzing data related to online user behavior, such as website traffic, user engagement, and online purchases.

Understanding the unique behavior of consumers is crucial for any business operating in Uzbekistan, especially Gulobod LLC, which produces yarn and textile products for the domestic market and export. Surveys, focus groups, ethnographic research, and online analytics are effective methods for studying consumer behavior and provide valuable insights into consumer preferences and attitudes. By using these methods, a company can tailor its products and services to the unique requirements of the Uzbek market and achieve long-term success.

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